

New records of Heteroptera from the Canary Islands (Spain), XXV

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ABSTRACT: The first record of *Gonocerus insidiator* (Fabricius, 1787) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae) on the island of Gran Canaria, the first record of *Halyomorpha halys* (Stål, 1855) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) on the island of Fuerteventura and the first record of *Menaccarus dohrnianus* (Mulsant & Rey, 1866) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) on the island of Lanzarote (Canary Islands, Spain) are reported. The distribution of the three species in the archipelago is summarised.

KEYWORDS: *Gonocerus insidiator*, *Halyomorpha halys*, *Menaccarus dohrnianus*, first records, distribution, Fuerteventura, Gran Canaria, Lanzarote, Canary Islands, Spain.

In the Canary archipelago (Spain), *Gonocerus insidiator* (Fabricius, 1787) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae) has been reported from the islands of La Palma and Tenerife, so far (Vázquez, 1986; Aukema et al., 2013; Roca-Cusachs et al., 2020). Herein, the first record of *G. insidiator* from the island of Gran Canaria is reported: On 31.12.2025, an adult specimen (Fig. 1) was observed in Playa del Inglés, a part of the municipality of San Bartolomé de Tirajana, located in the south of the island. A photograph of the specimen was uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Lerouge, 2026). The specimen was found in a garden of an apartment complex (coordinates: 27.7653087544, -15.556416635).

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Figure 1. Specimen of *Gonocerus insidiator* (Fabricius, 1787), Playa del Inglés, Gran Canaria, Canary Islands, Spain, 31.12.2025. (Photo: Frederik Lerouge).

Up to now, in the Canary archipelago *Halyomorpha halys* (Stål, 1855) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) has only been reported from the island of Tenerife (van der Heyden & Petrovan, 2023). Herein, the first record of the species from the island of Fuerteventura is reported: On 05.02.2026, a dead adult specimen of *H. halys* was found in Costa Calma, located in the municipality of Pájara in the southern part of the island (coordinates: 28.15235, -14.23070). A photograph of the specimen was uploaded to the online database Observation.org (Bekker, 2026).

Menaccarus dohrmianus (Mulsant & Rey, 1866) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) has been reported from the Canary islands of Gran Canaria and Fuerteventura, so far (Ribes, 1983; Aukema et al., 2006; Roca-Cusachs et al., 2020). Herein, the first record of the species from the island of Lanzarote is reported: On 24.04.2018, an adult specimen (Fig. 2) was observed in “El Jable”, an ecosystem of marine sands near Muñique (Fig. 3), located in the municipality of Teguisse (coordinates: 29.0681275951, -13.624107371). A photograph of the specimen was uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Gil, 2026).

Figure 2. Specimen of *Menaccarus dohrmianus* (Mulsant & Rey, 1866), “El Jable”, near Muñique, Lanzarote, Canary Islands, Spain, 24.04.2018. (Photo: Jaime Gil).

Figure 3. Ecosystem “El Jable”, habitat of *Menaccarus dohrnianus* (Mulsant & Rey, 1866), near Muñique, Lanzarote, Canary Islands, Spain. (Photo: Jaime Gil).

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